

THE PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECT IN THE STUDY OF ENGLISH FOR 1ST YEAR STUDENTS

Himmatova Nodira Normamatovna

The teacher at the Department of Uzbek Language and Literature, Termez
Institute of Agrotechnologies and Innovative Development

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7514499>

Introduction

Psychology is a science that studies the process of behavior and mental processes that occur in the brain of each person. Psychology is more needed than we think, because in fact, spiritual health and comfort is no less important than physical health. It is desirable that every teacher knows as much as possible about psychology and its aspects in teaching.

In order to obtain high-quality knowledge, psychological comfort is very important. It can be provided by knowledge of human psychology. Teachers should know more about the psychological aspect of education in order to ensure a high-quality and safe process of obtaining knowledge.

The basis of the concept of the learning process from a psychological point of view is related to the fact that students should receive only positive emotions from the learning process. The psychological process of learning should also be clear to parents, who should also treat their child and his education accordingly. Often there are problems that parents underestimate or overestimate the capabilities of their children, which will certainly affect their psychological state.

One of the problematic aspects of the psychology of learning is that a lot is required of children, and as a result they are poorly motivated. Some educational institutions do not have the necessary equipment for conducting lessons, there are no computers, furniture, and even there are no appropriate conditions (high-quality ventilation, lighting, heating, etc.). In this situation, it is difficult to prove to children that learning is important when adults themselves cannot prove it. And these are just a few proofs that the psychological aspect is important, since everything that happens happens first of all in our head.

The learning process is very complex and it is important to take into account the psychological attitude. It is important to tune in positively to this process, so as to get the most positive result. A person's thoughts materialize and therefore you need to tune in positively about learning, so that the process would allow you to get only positive emotions. Some face a certain fear that can arise for various reasons and manifest itself in training.

Knowledge of psychology is needed everywhere, especially when working with students. Unfortunately, not all teachers pay due attention to the psychological aspects of the learning process. They seem to be adults, but still live with some fears, face certain problems that sometimes arise because teachers do not take into account their psychophysiological characteristics.

Personality type

The psychological aspect is the aspect of the correct development of the personality. Healthy consciousness is a condition of mental health, which implies the type of temperament, character traits and level of intelligence, that is, the "ego" of a person as a whole.

Have you ever thought about the fact that success in learning English directly depends on the type of person's personality? Long-term studies of this topic demonstrate absolutely indisputable results, on the basis of which new teaching methods are being developed. We all know that people (from the point of view of psychology) are usually divided into introverts and extroverts. The latter are always sociable and open. These people are always happy to meet new people and do not hesitate to be the first to start a conversation. It has long been proven that it is extroverts who achieve results faster in learning foreign languages. Psychologists also say that extroverts love to take risks, and they are naturally gambling. This is also an undeniable plus, as it allows the teacher to offer new types of motivation, which will contribute to progress in learning. From all this it follows that extroverts really master spoken English faster, although this feature of theirs is not decisive. Systematics, discipline and perseverance are also indispensable here, but this no longer depends on what type of personality a person has.

For introverts, the main thing is to choose the right technique. In order for them to succeed, you need to use their natural ability to think logically. Of course, introverts pay less attention to speaking practice, have some problems with pronunciation, but as far as written translations and grammar are concerned, they are all right with this. Introverts manage to analyze the language, looking at it from the inside, and paying attention to every detail. This leads to absolute literacy and the absence of errors in speech and writing. Therefore, despite the fact that people with this type of personality are somewhat more difficult to communicate, they practically do not make mistakes, which gives them confidence.

Temperament

The temperament of a person determines the speed of assimilation of material, the formation of skills, the pace and rhythm of a person's daily activities, his emotionality. Moreover, our temperament directly affects memory, attention, perception. Agree, important factors in learning foreign languages. Psychophysiological features of the age of adolescents 16-17 years old

One should not forget to take into account the psychophysiological characteristics of age when teaching English.

It is important to start work with first-year students. The student's thinking acquires a personal, emotional character; intellectual activity here acquires a special affective coloring associated with self-determination and its desire to develop its own worldview.

Adolescents aged 16-17 are distinguished by their focus on the future, its expectation and foreboding. In order to choose a profession, he must correlate his capabilities with the requirements that a given professional activity imposes on a person.

At this age, there is an improvement in communication and general emotional well-being of the individual, a greater differentiation of his emotional reactions and ways of expressing emotional states, an increase in self-control and self-regulation.

These features of the development of a teenager are reflected in all types of his educational activities. In the classroom, he is distinguished by active thinking, a focus on solving mental problems, a taste for logical ordering and systematization, for the search for universal patterns, for independently finding ways of generalized orientation in the material, for theoretical generalizations. At this age, it is important for the student not to assimilate individual facts, particulars, details, but to understand the essence and meaning of the actions performed, he is interested in the synthesis of the part and the whole, the particular and the general, the concrete action and the general scheme of activity. Those forms of work in the classroom in which these tendencies find satisfaction turn out to be not only the most attractive for the student, but also the most productive. On the contrary, those forms that limit his activity to mechanical repetition and memorization meet his active internal resistance and, as a result, turn out to be unproductive.

They are impressed by such an organization of communication in the classroom, when there is a choice between different points of view, a comparison of alternative approaches, defending their point of view, a dispute. The only way to evoke a deep emotional and moral response in a teenager is to

put him in front of a problem that is close to him, forcing him to think and formulate a conclusion on his own.

So, we have considered the main psychophysical features of 1st year students: personality types, temperaments, age characteristics. Taking them into account in our work, we can increase the motivation of students and thereby improve the quality of teaching English.

Recommendations

It is well known that subjects studied even in the native language are not always accessible and interesting to the listener. To put it more precisely, the topics that students study are not always interesting to them. Therefore, it is recommended in the process of teaching a foreign language to choose topics that are accessible and interesting for each age and level of knowledge. As noted, the pace of speech of a native speaker, as a rule, seems too fast. Therefore, in order to grade the difficulties, one should start learning with the presentation of texts at a natural slow pace. However, often this pace is too fast for a beginner. In this case, without slowing down the pace of speech, one should lengthen the pauses between phrases. This will allow the student to eliminate the backlog of inner speech. It should be emphasized that the main way to overcome the difficulties associated with the characteristics of the listener's activity is: constant, regular and purposeful training of all components of this activity (auditory perception, short-term memory, inner speech, probabilistic forecasting) by performing appropriate exercises.

In order to overcome the difficulties associated with understanding the speech of native speakers, it is necessary to listen to their speech from the beginning of training, gradually reducing the number of texts presented by the teacher. The more different speakers (men, women, children) the student listens to, the easier it is for him to adapt to the individual manner of speech.

To acquire background knowledge, the student must receive the necessary information about the country of the language being studied and its people. It is known that modern foreign textbooks contain information of this kind. However, in domestic textbooks approved for teaching in general education institutions, such information is clearly not enough. Therefore, the teacher should communicate them, first of all, in texts for reading and listening, as well as with the help of films. Taking into account the peculiarities of the temperament of students, it should be noted that for children with all types of temperament, entertaining texts would be more suitable, but in this case, it is preferable to give different tasks.

Advice for overcoming speaking difficulties. The main recommendation may be to conduct lessons in the form of game situations, where students, performing various social functions, use both dialogue and monologue. But it must be taken into account that choleric and sanguine people, as a rule, speak with pleasure, and it is more difficult for phlegmatic and melancholic people to do this. Therefore, it is also necessary to vary tasks, offer interesting situations and call phlegmatic and melancholic people to talk.

As for reading, from a psychological point of view, the idea of the need to graduate material according to difficulty, gradually increasing the number of difficult-to-read words, is very significant.

Of exceptional importance is the readability of the text at the initial stage. The font at this stage should be large enough, clear, lines short.

In reading, the following recommendations can be offered: lessons of "error-free" reading, creating and maintaining a setting for reading accuracy, selecting material for reading accordingly, developing guess accuracy, conducting loud reading lessons.

The recommendation for overcoming difficulties in writing is as follows: it is necessary to develop in them the habit of controlling the grammatical and semantic side of what is written, it is also possible to introduce new methods to improve writing skills; the teacher can also suggest new interesting exercises (for example, write a short letter to your idol).

Conclusion

The problems of psychological improvement of the effectiveness of teaching a foreign language considered here were based on the need to change the basic approach to this process. The basis of such changes is based on the personal-activity approach. It lies in the fact that any specific goals of teaching English as a whole and each individual lesson are subject to the task of forming, developing, educating a student as a socially active, morally clean, convinced, able to independently set educational goals and achieve their solution to a person who knows how to collaborate and communicate effectively with others. Therefore, one of the main tasks in teaching English is based on purposefully orienting this process towards the personal development of the student. Teachers should distinguish the psychological characteristics of each student, try to convince them that learning a foreign language is available to absolutely everyone.

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